

HOW EFFECTIVE ARE AUDIO BOOKS FOR LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract:

This article is devoted to determining how effective the use of audio books is for foreign language learners and how important the role of teachers is in language learning. In learning a foreign language, the role of both audio books and teachers and their methodology is important, but which of the two is more important depends on you, what is on that level you want to study the lingo.

Key words: popularize language learning, audio books, intensive courses, teacher methodology

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We all know that today our country pays great attention to studying foreign languages. In particular, in accordance with the Decision of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich “On measures to bring the activities of popularization of overseas tongue learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a new level from a qualitative point of view”.

March 19, 2021, in Higher Education The lingo proficiency level C1 was Set for the teachers who are doing their work. Moreover, in order to effectively implement organizational measures to popularize the study of tongue, the Cabinet of Ministers made various decision and various projects are being implemented in this regard.

Currently, interest in learning languages is increasing day by, based on the demand of today’s time, Various procedure of educating foreign lingos have appeared. One of them is audio books that are widely used among young human. Audio books are intended for 5-6 months, during which time the learners will do listening and reading exercises for 2 hours a day. 6 months later, they can communicate in a alien tongue of their choice without memorizing any words or studying grammar rules, it is stated in the audio books advertisements. So, how accurate is this information? Is it really possible to study foreign lingos without any grammatical rules or memorizing words? Does this method of language learning work for everyone? Of course, it is very interesting to find answers to such questions. Nowadays, identical of these audio books are widely used among pupils in our country. The most popular among them are audio books under the “Booknomy” brand. Booknomy audio books have been operating since 2017. There is a simple rule 4 that is strictly required for intensive closes.

These are the following:

1. Listening and observation.
2. At least 2:30 hours of hearing.
3. Listen to each lesson for at last 7 days.

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4. Don't jump.

Of course, there are a number of views on booknomy intensive courses on social networks, someone else writes that this book is worthless. Audiobooks are fruitful if you are a listener who works with an audience and has a strong auditory inclination. There was a revision in persons who used this book. They will be able to speak at the level of ordinary, that is, A1.... A2. But as there are two sides of a can, using audio books does not regularly give the expected effect, one of the main causes for this is that the scholar's studying method is unfamiliar and he cannot master well the sentences he does not comprehend.

Before starting to study a new tongue, that is, a foreign lingo, everyone should determine which teaching method or method will be more effective. The biggest mistake in language studying is learning the wrong tongue, because if we start learning a lingo by mistake, then everything we study will have errors and shortcomings, and we will get used to admissions and these will become automatic in our brain, while everything we learned will become ineffective by itself. Therefore, for scholars who have just started the tongue, it is necessary to study at least a certain concept, that is the effect of creating a base. To acquire this skillfulness, we need the assist of educator.

The student, who has received the initial understanding and skills from the master, will achieve his desired goal if he works harder on himself. In the current developing period, a lot of modern innovative technique of teaching are being developed and classes are held based on the pupils level. Each lecturer has a various teaching so students have the right to learn from the educator they want, of course, the master work with the child is very significant. The teachers explain to lessons to us using the latest innovative methods, which help us study the tongue faster and more effectively. It should further be noted that a person most ask want he does not know. After all, there is a wonderful saying in our human "The one who does not know is a scholar by asking, and the one who does not inquire is a tyrant", therefore, a person should not be afraid of not knowing, but of not studying what he does not realize. In short, a human should work on himself in each aspect and strive towards his desired goal.

In conclusion, I do not want to say that using audio books is useless with these thoughts, on the contrary, audio books also help in tongue learning. Only, as we mentioned above, you can only reach A1 or A2 level with the assist of audio books, only in conversation. But it is very hard to achieve high result this level. A simple sample is that in the process of applying to higher Education institutions, applicants need at least B2 level. In order to obtain high-level certificate, we must take lessons from qualified masters, in any case, be it lingo studying or any other field, we need qualified tutors. They don't say for nothing: "Teacher is as great as your father". At the end of my speech, I would like to emphasize that our passionate teachers will be happy and healthy.

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